

THE INCIDENCE OF PERIODONTIC DISEASE IN THE ELDERLY

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Abstract: In this article, the origin, occurrence, gender and age of periodontitis in the elderly, and the prevention of the disease are approached from a scientific point of view.

Also, the high level of periodontal diseases of the population, the duration and severity of which lead to early loss of teeth and a decrease in the quality of life make it possible to remove this problem from the scope of medicine and give the problem an important social importance. role is important.

Key words: periodontitis, smoking, diabetes, tooth atrophy, soft tissue.

Relevance of the topic: In general, the development of periodontitis is caused by bad habits and general diseases, smoking, diabetes, gastrointestinal diseases, diseases of the cardiovascular system, stress, compression of the gums due to the appearance of alloy stones around the teeth, defects in the development of the jaw and palate, teeth caused by diseases such as improper growth, crooked teeth, and mouth breathing.

Today, one of the most common stomatological diseases is periodontitis, which is an inflammatory disease of the gums, which over time leads to atrophy of the bone and connective tissue of the gums, resulting in tooth decay and spontaneous loss of teeth.

The purpose of the work: as the purpose of the work, the occurrence, causes and spread of periodontitis in elderly people living in the city of Urganch were studied.

Research method and materials: as a research material, elderly people living in Urganch who applied to private clinics with complaints of toothache were studied and the following results were obtained.

Table 1 by gender.

When examined by gender, periodontitis was more common in men than in women, i.e. 60%. When people with periodontitis disease were studied in relation to age, it was found that it was mostly found in men aged 55-60. **Table 2.**

Examination results: the results of the examination showed that periodontitis is mainly found in elderly people aged 55-60 years, and the cause of the disease is that they do not follow the rules of dental hygiene in time.

Also, as a complication, the loss of teeth, as well as the absorption of toxins from microbes that caused periodontitis, cardiovascular system diseases, rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, and respiratory system diseases were also detected.

Conclusion: in conclusion, it can be said that periodontitis

disease is mainly due to non-observance of tooth brushing hygiene and failure to attend stomatological examinations on time, as well as spontaneous falling out of teeth and microbes in the oral cavity causing other diseases in our living body, i.e. diseases of the cardiovascular system, rheumatoid arthritis, atherosclerosis, respiratory system diseases .

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар:

1. Artikova D. O., Ruzmetova D. T. XORAZM VILOYATIDA HOMILADOR AYOLLARDA SIYDIK YO 'LLARI INFEKSIYASINI KECHISHI VA UNGA OLIB KELUVCHI OMILLAR //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 3-4.
2. Bekchanov A. J. et al. Causes of death in infants born to women affected by Covid-19 disease //American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149). – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 5. – С. 34-38.
3. Khasanovich K. R., Tulibaevna R. D., Ziyavovich T. H. DISTRIBUTION OF PERINATAL DISEASE IN NEWBORN CHILDREN IN KHORZAM PROVINCE BY CITY AND DISTRICT AND CAUSES OF DEATH //World Bulletin of Public Health. – 2021. – Т. 5. – С. 82-85.
4. Каримов Р., Авезов М. Оценка перинатальных случаев смерти, уровня и состояния заболеваний уха, горла и носа //Журнал вестник врача. – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 60-63.
5. Karimov R. X., Tursunov X. Z., Ruzmetova D. T. Modern approaches to perinatal disease in diabetes in pregnant women //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 12. – С. 173-179.
6. Karimov R. X, & Musaev U. M. (2023). ANALYSIS OF RESEARCH AND COMMISSION FORENSIC EXPERTISES CONDUCTED ON LIVING PERSONS. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149), 1(5), 61–63. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPMHS/article/view/423>
7. Каримов Р. Х., Мусаев У. М., Рuzметова Д. Т. ЯТРОГЕНИЯ НА ПРИМЕРАХ ИЗ ПРАКТИКИ (По данным лет обзор) //International conference on multidisciplinary science. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 10-12.
8. Каримов, Р. Х., Мусаев, У. М., Рuzметова, Д. Т., & Султанов, Б. Б. (2023, October). ЯТРОГЕНИЯ В НЕОНАТОЛОГИИ (ПО ДАННЫМ ЛЕТ. ОБЗОР). In International conference on multidisciplinary science (Vol. 1, No. 3, pp. 76-78).
9. Каримов Р. Х. и др. ВРАЧЕБНЫЕ ОШИБКИ В ПРАКТИКЕ АКУШЕРОВ-ГИНЕКОЛОГОВ //Past and Future of Medicine: International Scientific and Practical Conference. – 2023. – Т. 2. – С. 114-117.
10. Kh K. R. et al. PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPIRATORY AIRCRAFT CHANGES IN INFANTS BORN FROM MOTHERS WITH COVID-19 //JOURNAL OF HEALTHCARE AND LIFE-SCIENCE RESEARCH. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 21-28.
11. Матякубова С., Рuzметова Д. Особенности клинического течения при преждевременном излитии околоплодных вод и принципы ведения беременных //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2019. – №. 1 (107). – С. 175-177.
12. Матякубова С., Рuzметова Д. Фоновые факторы, влияющие на течение беременности и её исход при преждевременных разрывах плодных оболочек //Журнал проблемы биологии и медицины. – 2018. – №. 4 (104). – С. 203-205.
13. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. CLINICAL PRACTICAL ASSESSMENT APPLICATION OF POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION AS A TEST FOR ASSESSING MICROBIOCINOSIS IN PREGNANT WOMEN //Central Asian Journal of Pediatrics. – 2021. – Т. 2021. – №. 1. – С. 37-49.
14. Ruzmetova D. T., Matyakubova S. A. OCCURRENCE OF UTERINE

- MYOMA IN WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE IN KHOREZM REGION //Open Access Repository. – 2023. – Т. 4. – №. 3. – С. 489-492.
15. SA M., DT R. RISK FACTORS OF DEVELOPMENT OF PRETERM PREMATURE RUPTURE OF FETAL MEMBRANES IN PREGNANT WOMEN //European Science Review. – 2018. – Т. 1.
16. Sabirjanovich Y. B. et al. ETHERIOLOGICAL FACTORS OF DEATH IN PNEUMONIAS FOUND IN NEWBORNS //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF MODERN MEDICINE AND PRACTICE. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 8. – С. 1-4.
17. Сатликов Р.К, Юлдашев Б.С, Закиров Ш.Ю, Каримов Р.Х / ИЗУЧЕНИЯ МИКРОБИОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ МИКРООРГАНИЗМОВ ПРИ НЕОСЛОЖНЕННЫХ ИНФЕКЦИЯХ МОЧЕВЫХ ПУТЕЙ // Монография: - Т.: “O‘ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI” NMIU, 2022 – 84 б.
18. Перинатал ўлимнинг сабаблари ва патологик анатомияси / Монография / Х.З. Турсунов, Б.С. Юлдашев, Р.Х. Каримов: - Т.: “O‘ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI” NMIU, 2022 – 108 б.
19. Каримов Р.Х. / ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТИДА ПЕРИНАТАЛ ЎЛИМНИНГСАБАБЛАРИ ВА ПАТОЛОГИК АНАТОМИЯСИ // Автореферат: - Т: “Muxarririyat va nashriyot” бўлими, 2021 – 46 б.
20. Каримов Р.Х. / ХОРАЗМ ВИЛОЯТИДА ПЕРИНАТАЛ ЎЛИМНИНГСАБАБЛАРИ ВА ПАТОЛОГИК АНАТОМИЯСИ // Диссертация: - Т: “Muxarririyat va nashriyot” бўлими, 2021 – 111 б.
21. Tulibayevna R. D. Characteristics of Urogenital Tract Microbiota During Pregnancy //Research Journal of Trauma and Disability Studies. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 10. – С. 249-254.
22. Турсунов Х. З. и др. Бўйрак ва бўйрак усти беги касаллиги, уни даволаш усуллари ҳамда асоратлари (адабиётлар шарҳи). – 2022
23. Юлдашев Б. С., Каримов Р. Х., Бекчанов А. Ж. COVID-19 ЎТКАЗГАН ЧАҚАЛОҚЛАРДА ПНЕВМОНИЯНИНГ МОРФОЛОГИК ХУСУСИЯТИ //International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists" Sustainable Development: Problems, Analysis, Prospects"(Poland). – 2023. – С. 26-28.
24. Yuldashev B. S. et al. Causes of Pneumonia In Infants Born of Mothers Infected With Covid-19 //International Journal of Integrative and Modern Medicine. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 9-16.
25. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). OCCURRENCE OF CLINICAL PALATE AND LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research, 3(11), 80-85.
26. Юлдашев, Б. С., Исмаилов, О., Каримов, Р. Х., & Исмаилов, О. (2023). Хомила ва янги туғилган чақалоқлар мурдасининг суд тиббий экспертизаси (Текшируви). Ўқув қўлланма: Т.:“O ‘ZKITOBSAVDONASHRIYOTI” NMIU, 96.
27. Yuldashev, B. S., Kuruyazov, A. Q., Khodzhimuratov, O., & Karimov, R. X. (2023). A CASE OF LIP DEFECT WITH FACIAL ANOMALIES IN KHORAZM REGION. American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993-2149), 1(9), 547-552.
28. Sabirjanovich, Y. B., Khasanovich, K. R., Tulibaevna, R. D., & Safarboevich, R. S. (2024). RATE OF GLAUCOMA IN PENSION AGE CITIZENS (2023 in the example of the city of Urganch). International Journal of Alternative and Contemporary Therapy, 2(1), 4-7.